

Tiered Reactive Exploration Algorithm (TREA) in Independent versus Cooperative Role-Based Agent Robot Rescue Systems

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Abstract. Despite advances in autonomous robotics, the existing pathfinding algorithms used for search and rescue (SAR) still struggle to adapt in dynamic environments, resulting in delayed response and inefficient navigation. This study focuses on the development and implementation of a novel adaptive pathfinding algorithm in a simulated environment with improved real-time decision-making, route optimization, and adaptability to obstacles and dynamic terrain, that aims to enhance the performance of robotic agents in search and rescue scenarios. The newly developed pathfinding algorithm was tested in independent and cooperative role-based agent systems across varying robot counts, victim counts, and grid sizes. The results were then analyzed using a two-way ANOVA, which revealed that robot count and grid size significantly affected rescue completion time, and cooperative role-based agents outperformed independent ones, particularly in complex environments. The findings of this study demonstrate a significant improvement in navigation speed, obstacle avoidance, and agent coordination that contributes to the development of more reliable autonomous rescue operations and offers a scalable approach for implementing adaptive pathfinding in future SAR robotics, particularly in real-world disaster scenarios.

Keywords: pathfinding algorithm · breadth-first search · cooperative role-based agent · independent agent · search and rescue robot · simulated environment

1 Introduction

In every rescue mission, time is critical. Whether responding to natural disasters or emergencies, teams must act quickly, avoid danger, and ensure efficient operations to save lives. As technological advancements continue, robotic agents are increasingly deployed to assist in search and rescue (SAR), especially in areas that are inaccessible or unsafe for human responders [4].

These autonomous agents rely on pathfinding algorithms to navigate uncertain terrain, avoid hazards, and locate victims. Pathfinding algorithms are

essential to enable robots to perform independently or as part of a coordinated group in real-time rescue operations. Algorithms such as A*, D*, and D* Lite have been widely used in autonomous navigation due to their capability to compute optimal paths efficiently. Additionally, multi-agent systems are also used in search-and-rescue missions where multiple autonomous robots must coordinate in real time to divide tasks, avoid collisions, and efficiently locate victims. However, these widely used algorithms face limitations in dynamic settings. A* and D* depend heavily on predefined heuristics and static maps [2], reducing their adaptability when terrain conditions change. D* Lite improves on this by supporting real-time decision-making, but remains computationally intensive and does not scale well in multi-agent coordination scenarios [1,5,6]. These issues highlight the need for a pathfinding algorithm that can adapt to real-time environmental changes, maintain efficient navigation, and support seamless coordination between multiple robots with limited computational resources.

To address these challenges, this study proposes the Tiered Reactive Exploration Algorithm (TREA) for dynamic search and rescue (SAR) environments. TREA enhances real-time decision-making and multi-agent collaboration by basing its logic on the Breadth-First Search (BFS) because of its simplicity, reliability, and optimality in uniform-cost settings. Compared to heuristic-based methods like A*, BFS also enables predictable, layered exploration, making it easier to assign distinct roles or zones to cooperating agents[3]. To evaluate the efficiency of the proposed algorithm, simulations were conducted using both independent and cooperative role-based agents in a rescue environment to assess navigation speed, obstacle avoidance, and adaptability. The results of this study demonstrate the potential of TREA for scalable and efficient multi-agent rescue operations.

This study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the mean number of ticks of the TREA simulation in:
 - (a) Independent agent
 - (b) Cooperative role-based agents?
2. Is there a significant difference in the number of ticks between:
 - (a) Type (independent vs. Cooperative role-based)
 - (b) Robot Count
 - (c) Victim Count
 - (d) Grid Size?

1.1 Scope and Delimitation

This study focuses on evaluating the performance of TREA in independent and cooperative role-based agents in search and rescue simulations. It examines the effects of robot count (2 and 5), victim count (10, 25, 40), and grid size (20×20, 35×35, 50×50) on the number of ticks required to locate all victims. The simulation environment excludes real-world factors such as obstacles, communication delays, and robot failures, limiting the findings to controlled virtual settings.

1.2 Significance of the Study

This study will help to improve the pathfinding algorithms in **search and rescue (SAR) robotics**, particularly in dynamic and unpredictable environments. This will also help different **disaster-response agencies and NGOs** to gain faster, more reliable robotic support for planning and deploying rescue missions. This will also help **communities in disaster-prone regions** through the quicker victim detection and rescue in hazardous environment.

2 Methodology

2.1 Development

The Tiered Reactive Exploration Algorithm was developed in Python and based its logic on the Breadth-First Search (BFS) method because of its simplicity, reliability, and optimality in uniform-cost settings. It operates by exploring nodes level by level, making it suitable for structured search environments. The algorithm was applied to independent and cooperative multi-agent systems. In the independent setup, robots navigated individually without coordination. In contrast, the cooperative system used role-based agents that shared data and avoided task overlap for efficiency. To adapt BFS to dynamic simulations, periodic updates allowed agents to reassess paths based on victim detection or congestion. Trials were conducted across varying grid sizes, robot counts, and victim numbers to evaluate performance.

2.2 Procedure

A total of 162 simulation trials were conducted to evaluate the performance of the pathfinding algorithm. These trials tested various combinations of robot types (independent and cooperative), robot counts (2, 5, and 10), victim counts (10, 25, and 40), and grid sizes (20×20 , 35×35 , and 50×50). Each test was repeated multiple times to ensure consistency and reliability of the results, focusing on how efficiently agents could locate all victims within the simulated environment.

2.3 Statistical Treatment

The results were analyzed using the Jamovi statistical analysis application for a Two-Way ANOVA, followed by a post-hoc analysis to compare the number of ticks across different levels of robot count, victim count, and grid size.

3 Results

The mean tick count for independent runs was 556, whereas cooperative runs averaged only 324 ticks, indicating that coordinating multiple robots substantially speeds up task completion compared to having each robot operate alone.

Table 1. Mean number of Ticks

Type	Ticks
Independent	556
Cooperative	324

Using the two-way ANOVA, the results indicate that all factors have a significant effect on the number of ticks: Type (independent vs. cooperative) is $p < .001$, Robot count (2, 5, 10) is $p < .001$, Victim count (10, 25, 40) is $p = 0.042$, and Grid size is $p < .001$.

Table 2. ANOVA Results for Ticks

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
Type	2.17e+6	1	2.17e+6	37.98	< .001
Robot Count	7.73e+6	2	3.87e+6	67.73	< .001
Victim Count	368977	2	184488	3.23	0.042
Grid Size	1.17e+7	2	5.85e+6	102.49	< .001
Residuals	8.79e+6	154	57083		

The results for robot count were then further analyzed using Post-hoc tests which revealed that increasing from 2 to 5 robots reduced the tick count by 384 and from 2 to 10 by 515 ticks. The contrast between 5 and 10 robots, while smaller, remained significant ($p = 0.013$), confirming that each additional robot contributes to faster completion.

Table 3. Post Hoc Comparisons – Robot Count

Comparison	Mean Diff.	SE	df	t	p
2 – 5	384	46.0	154	8.34	< .001
2 – 10	515	46.0	154	11.20	< .001
5 – 10	131	46.0	154	2.86	0.013

For victim count, the comparison between 10 and 40 victims showed $p = 0.032$ which means that significantly increasing the number of victims affect the ticks duration. Meanwhile, the comparison of 10 vs 25 ($p = 0.482$) and 25 vs 40 ($p = 0.351$) contrasts are not significant, suggesting that tick duration is largely unaffected by moderate increases in victim number but lengthens when victim count rises to the highest tested level.

4 Discussion

The results of the study highlight the potential of TREA in improving the performance of autonomous robotic agents for search and rescue (SAR) scenarios

Table 4. Post Hoc Comparisons – Victim Count

Comparison	Mean Diff.	SE	df	t	p
10 – 25	-53.1	46.0	154	-1.15	0.482
10 – 40	-116.7	46.0	154	-2.54	0.032
25 – 40	-63.7	46.0	154	-1.38	0.351

Fig. 1. Figure 1 illustrates the variation in the number of ticks for independent and cooperative role-based agents. The independent agents show a wide spread of results, which means that their performance is less consistent and took significantly longer in some test. Meanwhile, the cooperative role-based agents have results that are more tightly grouped, indicating that it is faster and more consistent compared to independent.

Fig. 2. Figure 2 shows that cooperative role-based agents outperform independent agents in terms of efficiency and reliability. The cooperative system reduces redundancy, improves coordination, and results in faster victim rescues with less variability across trials.

by comparing independent and cooperative role-based agent systems across different robot counts, victim counts, and grid sizes.

The results show that both independent and cooperative role-based agents performed consistently across various factors, which means that TREA can be used effectively in different SAR conditions. However, the cooperative role-based agents consistently performed better than the independent ones. This shows that TREA helps improve agent coordination, decision-making, and route optimization, especially in dynamic environments.

Although all the factors were found to significantly affect the number of ticks, the post hoc analysis gave more specific details. For robot count, the results show that increasing the number of robots leads to faster completion of tasks. This shows that the system is scalable and can handle larger groups of agents. On the other hand, for the victim count, only a large increase in the number of victims caused a significant rise in ticks. This means the system stays efficient under normal conditions but might need to be improved for very large rescue scenarios.

However, the generalizability of the results is limited by the study's scope, as the pathfinding algorithm was implemented in a simulated environment and not compared against other existing algorithms. While this limits direct application in real-world conditions, the findings remain valid in demonstrating TREA's potential for SAR operations.

It is beyond the scope of this study to evaluate the algorithm's performance in physical and real-life disaster scenarios. Therefore, the researchers recommend that future developers implement and test TREA in real-world environments to validate its effectiveness and practicality for real-life deployment in SAR missions.

5 Conclusion

This study concludes that TREA has great potential as a pathfinding algorithm for real-life search and rescue (SAR) missions. It improves the coordination, decision-making, and efficiency of autonomous agents, making it a promising approach for future rescue operations in dynamic and complex environments.

For future development, it is recommended to collaborate with disaster response agencies to better understand real-world challenges and requirements. Implementing TREA in actual SAR scenarios will help validate its performance beyond simulation and improve its program based on comments from real-life implementation. With further testing and improvement, TREA can become a reliable tool in supporting rescue teams and reducing the impact of disasters on affected communities.

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